
THE EFFECT OF NONLINEARITY ON PERFORMANCE IN NEURAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

In artificial neural networks (ANNs), element-wise nonlinearities are essential. In the absence of nonlinearities, adding multiple layers cannot overcome the limitations of a single linear layer. Here I have studied the amount of nonlinearity a network needs to function effectively. By employing a parameterized version of the "leaky ReLU" function, I examined how smoothly transitioning from nonlinear to linear affects network performance, in the context of the MNIST character recognition problem. I find that the network's performance is surprisingly robust to the reduction of nonlinearity until it is nearly linear, i.e. even a slight nonlinearity is sufficient. Furthermore, adding multiple layers does not change the sensitivity to the amount of nonlinearity. This study suggests that although nonlinearity is essential to good performance, not much is needed.

1 Introduction

In the field of machine learning, artificial neural networks (ANNs) play a crucial role. As demonstrated more than half a century ago by Minsky and Papert ([Marvin and Seymour, 1969](#)), the power of ANNs derives from their nonlinearity. Linear networks can only perform a small fraction of all possible tasks, whereas nonlinear networks can in principle approximate any function.

Here I address the following question: How nonlinear does a nonlinear network have to be in order to work effectively? I formulate this problem in the context of the MNIST character recognition problem ([LeCun, 1998](#)). To allow me to ask this in a quantitative fashion, I have used a parameterized version of network nonlinearity that moves smoothly from the standard nonlinearity to a purely linear version.

Specifically, to achieve a smooth transition from a nonlinear to a linear network, I use a "leaky ReLU" function. The standard ReLU is a function whose output is equal to its input for positive inputs and 0 for negatives inputs. The leaky ReLU modifies this for negative inputs, so that it maps negative inputs linearly to negative outputs, but with a small slope (less than 1). Conveniently for the present work, if the slope is 1, then the leaky ReLU becomes a linear transfer function, and the network is now linear. Thus, the slope of the nonlinearity allows the network to smoothly approach and eventually equal a linear network.

My key finding is that reducing the degree of nonlinearity exerts only a small effect on performance until it becomes very close to linear.

2 Problem Formulation

Notation

I denote the weight matrix associated with layer i as $W^{(i)}$ and the bias vector as $b^{(i)}$. The input to layer i is represented as $x^{(i)}$ and its output as $y^{(i)}$. The activation function is denoted as $f(\cdot)$.

Leaky ReLU

Figure 1: Leaky ReLU. When $\theta = 0^\circ$, the function is the standard ReLU; when $\theta = 45^\circ$, the function is linear. For intermediate values it smoothly interpolates.

In a multilayer linear network, the output of each layer is obtained through linear transformations. The output of layer i can be represented as:

$$y_{lin}^{(i)} = W^{(i)}x^{(i)} + b^{(i)}$$

For a non-linear network, the output of each layer is obtained through non-linear transformations activated by applying a non-linear function, such as leaky ReLU, to a linear transformation of the input. The output of layer i can be given by:

$$y_{nonlin}^{(i)} = f(W^{(i)}x^{(i)} + b^{(i)})$$

The leaky ReLU function is defined as:

$$f(z; \theta) = \begin{cases} z & \text{if } z > 0 \\ \tan(\theta) \cdot z & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where θ is an angle measured in degrees and $0 \leq \theta \leq 45^\circ$. At $\theta = 0^\circ$, we recover the standard ReLU function:

$$f(z; 0^\circ) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } z < 0 \\ z & \text{if } z \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

And at $\theta = 45^\circ$, the function is linear for all inputs:

$$f(z; 45^\circ) = z.$$

For all other intermediate values of θ , it the function smoothly interpolates between the linear and fully nonlinear cases.

3 Results

To examine the relationship between the degree of nonlinearity given by θ and test accuracy for MNIST, I systematically varied theta across its full range from 0° - 45° . As my initial test, I used a network with the following architecture. After the initial input layer consisting of 784 inputs, there were three layers, each of which consisted of 128 units, followed by a final output layer consisting of 10 units. Each network was trained for 50 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 100. Each run was repeated 5 times. Code was written in PyTorch with the assistance of ChatGPT-4 and run in a free Colab notebook.

Fig. 2 shows the relationship between theta and test accuracy, where test accuracy is defined as the "percent correct" on examples not in the training set. When $\theta = 0^\circ$, i.e. the leaky ReLU is a perfect ReLU and network performance is maximal (about 98%). When $\theta = 45^\circ$, i.e. when the leaky ReLU is a perfect linear network, network performance

Figure 2: Network performance falls off with decreasing nonlinearity. Figure shows test accuracy as a function of the degree of nonlinearity θ , where $\theta = 0^\circ$ is a perfect ReLU and $\theta = 45^\circ$ is a perfect linear network.

is minimal (about 92%). Linear performance is still well above chance which is 10%. Interesting, performance only decreased gradually up to about $\theta = 30^\circ$, afterwards it dropped off quite rapidly. In other words, even a slight nonlinearity is sufficient to produce good performance. These results confirm the importance of the nonlinearity for good performance on this task and quantify the degree of nonlinearity needed to achieve good performance.

The results described above were for a three-layer network. I wondered how my results depended on the number of layers. I hypothesized that networks with fewer layers would be show a fall-off of performance for smaller angles of θ ; in other words, that shallow networks would require more nonlinearity to achieve high performance. Fig. 3 compares networks with 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 layers. Surprisingly, all of the networks performed about equally well. In fact, the only condition where a striking difference was seen among the results was the 10-layer linear network. However, since a series of even 10 linear layers can be replaced by a single linear layer, this deviation cannot be due to the nonlinear angle parameter θ . Instead, it might arise from numerical issues with the gradient descent algorithm used.

4 Discussion

I have explored how the degree of nonlinearity in (ANNs) affects performance. My approach was to smoothly vary from the standard nonlinearity to no nonlinearity using the leaky ReLU. The key findings are (1) Even a slight degree of nonlinearity in the network results in substantial performance. Performance only begins to diminish appreciably as the network approaches a near-linear state; and (2) Contrary to my initial expectations, the depth of the network (i.e., the number of layers) did not significantly alter the relationship between nonlinearity and performance.

There are several caveats to the current findings. First, the findings were limited to the MNIST character recognition problem. It remains to be seen if similar trends would hold for other datasets, especially those of larger complexity or from different domains. Second, it is possible that the results depend in some way on the optimization algorithm used. The fact that the performance for the deep 10-layer linear network was different from the results for 1-5 layers suggest there might be some issues there. To address these issues, it would be useful to expand the results to other data sets, other optimization algorithms, and other nonlinearities beyond ReLU.

In conclusion, while the significance of nonlinearity in ANNs has long been understood, my study provides a nuanced understanding of its quantitative impact. As we move forward in the age of deep learning, such insights will be invaluable in shaping the design and application of neural networks.

Figure 3: Sensitivity to nonlinearity is independent of the number of layers. Performance vs nonlinearity for 1, 2, 3, 5, 10 layers. Surprisingly, the number of layers has almost no effect on the sensitivity to θ

References

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